

Additional Information about the Article

Theoretical Basis

The Privacy Requirements Pattern Catalog is composed of 3 types of Software Patterns. Figure 1 shows an example of a Functional Requirement Pattern - FRP; Figure 2 shows an example of a Non-Functional Requirement Pattern - NFRP; and Figure 3 shows an example of an Acceptance Test Pattern - ATP.

Padrão de Requisito Funcional: FRP_Disponibilizar_Finalidade

Author: Cinara Gomes de Melo Carneiro
Context: Controlador disponibiliza finalidade do tratamento dos dados pessoais
Forces: O controlador tem obrigação de disponibilizar finalidade do tratamento dos dados pessoais
Problem: O controlador precisa disponibilizar a finalidade do tratamento dos dados pessoais
Solution: O controlador pode disponibilizar a finalidade do tratamento dos dados pessoais
Source: LGPD - Lei Geral de Proteção de Dados Pessoais. Art.9 I
Version: 1.0

Bag: SPB_Tratamento_de_Dados_Pessoais_REQUISITOS

Feature: Feature_DisponibilizarFinalidade
As: Controlador
I can: Disponibilizar a finalidade do tratamento dos dados pessoais
So that: O titular possa acessar

Scenario: Scenario_DisponibilizarFinalidadeComSucesso
Given: Disponibilizar finalidade do tratamento dos dados pessoais
When: Eu informar o <domínio> e selecionar <publicar>
Then: A finalidade será disponibilizada e uma <mensagem> será exibida

Examples
"www.antoniaegabriellyfotografiasme.com.br/políticaprivacidade |true | "A finalidade do tratamento foi disponibilizada !"

Figure 1: Example of FRP

Padrão de Requisito Não Funcional: NFRP_Disponibilizar_Forma_De_Forma_Clara_Adequada_Ostensiva

Author: Cinara Gomes de Melo Carneiro
Context:
Forces:
Problem: O controlador deverá disponibilizar a forma de tratamento ao titular de forma clara, adequada e ostensiva
Solution: Definir uma política para disponibilizar a forma de tratamento de dados ao titular
Source: LGPD - Lei Geral de Proteção de Dados Pessoais. Art.9 II
Version: 1.0

Bag: SPB_Tratamento_de_Dados_Pessoais_REQUISITOS

System property: Política para disponibilizar a Forma de forma clara, adequada e ostensiva
Description: Usar recursos para que a forma seja identificada facilmente pelo titular dos dados, com por exemplo, colocar em negrito. Apresentar de forma objetiva e compreensível, sem uso de jargões ou termos técnicos que possam dificultar a compreensão do titular, adequadas ao contexto de uso.

Figure 2: Example of NFRP

Padrão de Teste de Aceitação: ATP_DisponibilizarFinalidade
<p>Author: Cinara Gomes de Melo Carneiro Context: Controlador disponibiliza finalidade do tratamento dos dados pessoais Forces: O controlador tem obrigação de disponibilizar finalidade do tratamento dos dados pessoais Problem: É preciso garantir que a finalidade do tratamento dos dados sejam disponibilizadas Solution: Testar se a finalidade do tratamento dos dados está sendo disponibilizada Source: LGPD - Lei Geral de Proteção de Dados Pessoais. Art.9 I Version: 1.0</p> <p>Bag: SPB_Tratamento_de_Dados_Pessoais_REQUISITOS</p>
<p>Test Case: Scenario_DisponibilizarFinalidadeComSucesso Given: Disponibilizar finalidade do tratamento dos dados pessoais When: Eu informar o <dominio> e selecionar <publicar> Then: A finalidade será disponibilizada e uma <mensagem> será exibida Example:</p>
<p>Input "www.antoniaegabriellyfotografiasme.com.br/politicaprivacidade " true</p>
<p>Output "A finalidade do tratamento foi disponibilizada !"</p>

Figure 3: Example of NFRP

Assessment Instruments

Initially, respondents were asked to complete the Informed Consent Form and the profile questionnaire in order to verify their preliminary information, as well as their level of knowledge about Electronic Revenue Management (ERM) and the General Data Protection Law (LGPD). These questionnaires are included in this file and have been named as follows:

- 1 - TCLE.pdf
- 2 - Profile - Stu- ENG.pdf
- 5 - Profile - Prof- ENG.pdf

The Informed Consent Form contains parts of the text that are presented in sequence due to anonymization.

To evaluate the CPRP, the NASA TLX questionnaire was used to assess student workload. The TAM questionnaire was used by students to evaluate ease of use and usefulness. With professionals, the TAM questionnaire was applied to assess their perception of CPRP use, considering ease of use, usefulness, and intention to use. These questionnaires are included in this file and have been named as follows:

- 3 - TAM - Stu - ENG.pdf

- 4 - NASA TLX - Stu - ENG.pdf
- 6 - TAM - Prof- ENG.pdf

Controlled Experiment Scenario

In a controlled experiment with students, a script was developed that presented a fictitious scenario. This scenario consisted of a school needing to implement an enrollment management system. The enrollment process was manual, causing several problems, such as lost documents, difficulty accessing information, and communication failures with parents/guardians. Therefore, the creation of a system to manage the data was proposed, which should comply with the General Data Protection Law (LGPD).

Thus, the proposed activity was to elicit privacy requirements relevant to: 1) The enrollment process; and 2) Registering, modifying, searching, and deleting personal data of students, parents/guardians, teachers, and staff. The experimental group used the CPRP (Critical Process Control Report) as support, and the control group used the LGPD in its entirety.

In addition, the script provided the data that would be collected, the purpose of the processing, the data retention period, with whom the data would be shared, other complementary information, and the document to be delivered at the end of the experiment.

File 7 - Scenario - Controlled Experiment.pdf contains the document that the students used.

Qualitative Analysis of the Controlled Experiment

In the controlled experiment, the analysis was divided into two main groups: contributions and challenges. The network generated from the qualitative analysis of the open-ended questions is presented in the file Rede - Disc - Geral.pdf.

The contributions were divided into 3 categories:

- Contri_Conhecimento_Disc: This category sought to classify and categorize responses that report contributions related to student knowledge, that is, to show that the topic presented to the students provided the development and learning of new knowledge;
- Contri_Estrutura_CPRP: This category sought to classify and categorize responses that report contributions related to the structure of the CPRP, that is, to show that,

through the students' responses, the structure of the CPRP was well accepted and easy to understand;

- **Contri_Beneficios_CPRP:** This category sought to classify and categorize responses that report contributions related to the quality of the CPRP, that is, to show that, through the students' responses, benefits of using the CPRP were reported and justifications were given to demonstrate the importance of using the CPRP.

The contributions reported and classified according to structure highlight positive aspects of the CPRP, such as clarity in the objective of the FRP and NFRP (1 - D5), concise structure (2 - D3, D30), relevant and detailed information (2 - D28, D30), and easily accessible language (1 - D17).

Regarding the benefits of the CPRP, characteristics that favored its use were identified, notably assistance in the reuse of RPs (3 - D7, D22, D29), theoretical basis grounded in the LGPD (3 - D9, D12, D24), and guidance with practical examples (5 - D8, D12, D18, D20, D26). Also mentioned were the ease of eliciting requirements for PRs in compliance with the LGPD (2 - D11, D27), standardization of requirements (3 - D13, D24, D29), scenarios for the use of PRs (1 - D8), and usefulness for eliciting/specifying PRs (2 - D14, D21).

Regarding the students' knowledge, it was found that the use of the CPRP contributed to expanding knowledge about LGPD (3 - D10, D16, D23), about PRs (1 - D27), and the integration of the two subjects (2 - D19, D21).

In this group, the challenges were divided into 3 categories:

- **Desa_Conhecimento_Disc:** This category sought to classify and categorize responses that report challenges related to student knowledge, that is, to show that many students had difficulty due to a lack of knowledge about the subject (LGPD and ER);
- **Desa_Experiencia_Usuario:** This category sought to classify and categorize responses that report challenges related to user experience, more precisely regarding the structure, interaction, interface, and usability of the CPRP, that is, to show that many students had difficulty understanding the structure of the CPRP, justifying reasons, whether due to lack of responsiveness, usability, and research;
- **Desa_Experimento:** This category sought to classify and categorize responses that report challenges related to the objective of the experiment, that is, to show that,

through the students' responses, it was reported that some students had difficulty understanding the objective of the experiment, that the limited contact with the CPRP may have interfered with the execution of the proposed activities, and that the amount of information in the first contact.

The challenges reported and classified regarding student knowledge are: lack of knowledge about LGPD and ER (2 - D17, D27), knowledge to understand essential requirements (1 - D2), and identification of use (1 - D26), which may have influenced the use of CPRP.

Regarding user experience, it was possible to classify the difficulty in understanding the structure of CPRP (9 - D6, D7, D9, D14, D18, D21, D22, D24, D2), which can be justified by the difficulty in using the bags in the user's context (2 - D10, D13), lack of a search mechanism (4 - D8, D11, D18, D31), lack of clarity of information (1 - D5), unintuitive interface (3 - D6, D28, D29), lack of responsiveness (1 - D3), and difficulty in usability (5 - D6, D8, D12, D28).

Given this, some students reported that they had difficulty understanding the experiment (1 - D20), which can be justified by the amount of information presented in the first contact with the experiment (2 - D19, D30) and by the little contact with the CPRP (1 - D9).

Qualitative Analysis of Usage Perception Assessment

In the usage perception assessment, the analysis was divided into 3 main groups: benefits, challenges, and suggestions. The general network generated from the qualitative analysis of the open-ended questions is presented in the file Rede - Prof - Geral.pdf.

Within this group, the benefits were divided into 5 categories:

- Bene_Conhecimento_Prof: This category sought to classify and categorize responses that report benefits related to the professionals' knowledge, that is, to show that the topic presented to the professionals generated knowledge for them;
- Bene_Contri_CPRP: This category sought to classify and categorize responses that report the benefits of the perception of CPRP use, that is, to show the benefits of using CPRP in activities related to requirements engineering in accordance with the LGPD;

- Bene_Estrutura_CPRP: This category sought to classify and categorize responses that report benefits related to the CPRP structure, that is, to show the positive points of the CPRP structure that were presented by the professionals;
- Bene_Exp_Usu: This category sought to classify and categorize responses that report benefits related to the user experience with CPRP, that is, to show the points observed by professionals that provided better engagement of professionals and strengthened the relationship with the use of CPRP;
- Bene_LGPD_CPRP: This category sought to classify and categorize responses that report benefits related to the LGPD (Brazilian General Data Protection Law) from the use of CPRP, that is, to show the points perceived about the LGPD in the catalog.

The reported and classified benefits regarding professional knowledge were: understanding of the LGPD (2 – P1, P4). Regarding the contributions of using CPRP, responses highlighted its role in aiding the understanding of PRs (3 – P2, P4, P6) and in specifying PRs (2 – P3, P6), as well as presenting practical examples of PRs (2 – P3, P5). Also mentioned were the ease of applying ATPs (1 – P1) and eliciting PRs (2 – P5, P6), preventing the omission of relevant information (1 – P5), reusing PRs (3 – P2, P3, P5), useful for eliciting PRs (1 – P6), and verifying the existence of PRs in projects (1 – P4).

Regarding the structure, it was presented that the CPRP structure is clear and concise (1 - P4), the language is easily accessible (1 - P1), the texts are similar to those used in development environments (1 - P4), and it is well-organized, both from a general perspective (1 – P1) and in the grouping of bags (3 – P3, P4, P6).

Regarding the benefits related to user experience, professionals perceived ease in consulting RPs (1 - P4), navigation (2 - P4), identification of RPs (2 - P2, P6), and strengthening of communication between FS professionals (1 - P3). Furthermore, benefits related to the LGPD were observed, where professionals perceived that the CPRP converted the LGPD into PRs (1 - P3) and, in the professionals' view, the catalog is in compliance with the LGPD PRs (4 - P4, P5).

In this group, the challenges were divided into 3 categories:

- Desaf_Conhecimento_Prof: This category sought to classify and categorize responses that report challenges related to the professional's knowledge, that is, to show the

difficulties that professionals had in understanding the structure of the CPRP, caused by a lack of knowledge on the subject (LGPD and ER);

- **Desaf_Exp_Usuario:** This category sought to classify and categorize responses that report challenges related to user experience, more precisely on the structure, interaction and usability of the CPRP, that is, to show that many professionals had difficulties in understanding the structure of the CPRP;
- **Desa_Introducao_CPRP:** This category sought to classify and categorize responses that report challenges perceived in the first contact with the CPRP, that is, to present situations that may have hindered professionals from understanding the CPRP because they were not present in the introduction to the CPRP.

The challenges reported and classified regarding the professionals' knowledge revealed gaps related to a lack of knowledge about ATP, FRP, NFRP, BDD, and Gherkin (1 - P5), as well as difficulty in understanding the LGPD (1 - P1). As a consequence, a series of difficulties emerged, such as identifying the use of standards (1 - P5), interpreting the nomenclature of standards (2 - P5, P6), mapping relevant standards (2 - P3, P5), using CPRP in projects (1 - P5), and verifying the suitability of PRs to the project context (1 - P3).

Regarding user experience, difficulties were identified in understanding and locating RPs (1 - P3), generic presentation of features and scenarios (1 - P4), lack of traceability in PRs (2 - P2), usability problems (1 - P3), repetition of information between RPs, scenarios, and features (1 - P4), and the fact that the professional did not work with RPs (1 - P6).

Furthermore, some professionals reported difficulties in their first contact with the CPRP, pointing out the need for prior study to understand the CPRP structure (1 - P4). The large amount of information/standards in the CPRP was also mentioned (1 - P3), as well as the lack of an introductory explanation of the LGPD (1 - P4) and of terms and nomenclature (1 - P4).

In this group, the suggestions were divided into 3 categories:

- **Sug_Aplicação_CPRP:** This category sought to classify and categorize responses that report suggestions related to the application of CPRP in activities related to ER, that is, situations that can facilitate the use of CPRP;
- **Sug_Estrutura_CPRP:** This category sought to classify and categorize responses that report suggestions related to the structure, presenting situations to improve CPRP, that

is, to facilitate the understanding of the structure by users in their first contact with CPRP;

- Sug_Exp_Usu_CPRP: This category sought to classify and categorize responses that report suggestions related to the user experience, more precisely about the usability of CPRP, that is, to show ways to improve the usability and interaction of the user with CPRP.

With the goal of improving the application of CPRP, professionals suggested several improvements. Among them, the following stand out: offering applied environment (1 - P5), developing a checklist to verify the principles of the LGPD (3 - P1, P3, P5), creating editable templates for PRs (1 - P5), and developing a screen that presents the basic RPs of the project. Also mentioned were the inclusion of a summary of the data analysis (1 – P1), quick tips for using standards in projects (1 – P5), a support tool for clarifying doubts (1 – P2) and encouraging the use of RPs (1 – P5), in addition to integration with the Requirements Engineering process (3 – P2, P4, P5) and with tools used in daily practice (2 – P3, P5).

Regarding user experience, suggestions included grouping PRs by similarity (2 - P3, P5), implementing a screen with the most used patterns (1 - P5), usability improvements (1 - P6), creating natural language interaction (1 - P6), including search mechanisms (3 - P1, P5), and using tooltips to clarify technical terms (1 - P4).

Regarding the structure of the CPRP, professionals recommended presenting features and scenarios close to reality (1 - P4), creating a simplified guide with essential information (1 - P5), using everyday terms instead of technical terms (1 - P4), an introductory explanation of the LGPD (1 - P4) and of terms and nomenclatures (1 - P4).